

Studies in Acenaphthenone. Part II.

Indole and Acridine Derivatives.

BY ANUKUL CHANDRA SIRCAR AND M. D. RAJA GOPALAN.

In the first paper in this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 103) the preparation of pyrilium derivatives from acenaphthenone has been described. The present paper deals with the preparation and properties of indole and acridine derivatives from acenaphthenone.

The $\text{-CH}_2\text{-CO-}$ group in acenaphthenone has now been utilised for the preparation of indole derivatives by following the procedure indicated by Robinson and Thornley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 3145). Acenaphthindole and N-methyl- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthindole have been prepared by condensing phenylhydrazine and unsymmetrical methylphenylhydrazine respectively with acenaphthenone.

N-Methyl $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthindole.

The condensation of aromatic *o*-aminoaldehydes with substances containing the group $\text{-CH}_2\text{-CO-}$ to quinolines by means of dilute sodium hydroxide constitutes one of the important methods for the synthesis of such bodies (Friedlander, *Ber.*, 1882, **15**, 2573; 1883, **16**,

1888; 1892, 25, 1752). Baeyer and Drewson (*Ber.*, 1888, 16, 2207) instead of using *o*-aminoaldehydes obtained quinolines by the reduction under suitable conditions of the corresponding nitro derivatives.

By following the method of Friedlander (*loc. cit.*), pheno- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthacridine (I) has now been prepared by the condensation of

(I)

o-aminobenzaldehyde with acenaphthenone. In an attempt to prepare the same compound by the reduction of the condensation product of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and acenaphthenone (*cf.* Baeyer and Drewson, *loc. cit.*) the desired product was obtained only in extremely poor yield. The major portion was converted into a red substance, and it appears that the reduction had gone one stage further and the corresponding dihydro derivative had been formed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acenaphthindole.—Acenaphthenone (1 g.) and phenylhydrazine (0.65 g.) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for about 2-3 hours. After an hour the solution was found to change colour from pale yellow to deep yellow and then to orange red and gradually fine golden yellow shining plates began to separate. At the end of 3 hours it was found

that a large quantity of yellow plates had deposited. The solution was then diluted with 2—3 c.c. of water and again heated on a water-bath for about 1 hour when more crystals collected. These were filtered and purified by recrystallisation from dilute alcohol in which it is fairly soluble. It forms beautiful golden yellow shining plates, m.p. 235°. It is highly soluble in benzene, chloroform, ether, etc. It gives a blue coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid, and is reprecipitated on dilution. Alcoholic hydrochloric acid can also effect the elimination of ammonia and consequent ring closure. (Found: N, 6.12. $C_{18}H_{17}N$ requires N, 5.8 per cent.).

N-Methyl- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthindole.—Acenaphthenone (1 g.) and unsymmetrical methylphenylhydrazine (0.8 g.) were dissolved in acetic acid (10 c.c.) and refluxed on a boiling water-bath for 3-4 hours. At the end of about an hour the colour of the solution began to change from orange to deep red and on the heating being continued for some more time, a little of a scarlet red crystalline precipitate began to separate. A little more acetic acid (3 c.c.) was added and the refluxing continued for another 3 hours by which time sufficient quantity of crystals had deposited. These were filtered and recrystallised from boiling acetic acid by the addition of hot water. On cooling, beautiful scarlet-red plates separated, m.p. 204°. It is fairly soluble in alcohol or acetic acid and very soluble in chloroform or benzene. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid imparting to it a dirty green colour. (Found: N, 5.84. $C_{19}H_{13}N$ requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

Pheno- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthacridine.—Acenaphthenone (0.7 g.) and *o*-aminobenzaldehyde (0.5 g.) (prepared by Friedlander's method, *loc. cit.*) were dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and to the cold solution a few drops of 10 per cent. alcoholic potash were added. The sides of the vessel on being scratched, golden yellow plates separated. After keeping the reaction mixture for an hour in a cool place, the crystals were filtered and washed with 40 per cent. alcohol. It was purified by dissolving in hot alcohol and to the solution hot water was added slowly when, at a particular dilution, clustres of shining golden yellow plates separated all on a sudden. The crystals were filtered, washed and dried, m.p. 181°. It is soluble in benzene, chloroform or acetic acid, etc. It gives a straw yellow colour with concentrated sulphuric acid from which it is not reprecipitated on dilution. The substance is soluble in hot concentrated hydrochloric acid from which yellow silky needles of

the hydrochloride separate on cooling. (Found: N, 5.98. $C_{19}H_{11}N$ requires N, 5.53 per cent.).

Attempts to Prepare Pheno- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthacridine by the Reduction of o-Nitrobenzilideneacenaphthenone.

o-Nitrobenzilideneacenaphthenone.

Equimolecular quantities of acenaphthenone and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde were dissolved in the smallest quantity of alcohol and a few drops of 10 per cent. alcoholic potash added. The solid product that separated after some time was filtered, washed with 40 per cent. alcohol, and dissolved in boiling alcohol followed by the addition of animal charcoal and filtered hot. The filtrate, on dilution with a few drops of water deposited on cooling deep yellow shining needles, m.p. 157°. It is highly soluble in benzene or chloroform. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish violet colour. (Found: N, 4.73. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

Reduction of o-nitrobenzilideneacenaphthenone.— *o*-Nitrobenzilideneacenaphthenone (0.5 g.) was dissolved in hot absolute alcohol (20-25 c.c.). When the substance had all dissolved about 1 c.c. of fuming hydrochloric acid was added and 0.3 g. of iron dust (reduced by hydrogen) was then introduced in small quantities at a time. Immediately a pinch of iron was added vigorous action ensued and the solution turned red. After the reaction had ceased and the solution was boiling for 10 minutes, another small quantity of iron was added. After some time a red precipitate began to appear and when all the iron had been added the mixture was kept boiling for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The whole operation took about 2 hours. The precipitate was filtered hot and washed first with water and then repeatedly extracted with concentrated hydrochloric acid by boiling. The hydrochloric acid extract on cooling separated some fine silky needles identified to be the hydrochloride of pheno- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthacridine. But the yield was very poor.

The red precipitate left after extraction with hydrochloric acid was dissolved in acetone and filtered from any unchanged iron or iron oxide. On addition of hot water to the acetone solution a brownish-red amorphous precipitate was obtained. It could not be crystallised from any solvent. It is sparingly soluble in chloroform or alcohol. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid imparting to it a violet coloration. Like the dihydroacridines it is insoluble in hydrochloric acid, *i.e.*, has no basic properties. It decomposes between 236-40°. From its properties it is definite that the substance is not pheno- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthacridine. (Found: N, 5.58. The acridine requires N, 5.53 and its dihydro derivative requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

When silver nitrate was added to an alcoholic solution of the above reduction product (*cf.* Graebe and Caro, *Annalen*, 1871, 158, 278) the red colour disappeared and a pale yellow solution resulted. On filtering the precipitated silver and diluting the solution, a yellow substance was obtained which melted between 160-70°, though not sharply. The yield being poor it could not be further investigated. This substance might be the desired oxidation product, *vis.*, pheno- $\alpha\beta$ -acenaphthacridine in a very impure form. But in the absence of further proof no definite constitution can be assigned to the red reduction product.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received April 22, 1932.

